

Effects of Maternal Nutrition at Different Stages of Pregnancy in Bali Cows on Growth Performance of the Offspring to Weaning

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Abstract : The objective of this study was to investigate the life-long effect of in utero nutrition fed at different stages of pregnancy in Bali cows (n = 40): (U1) without in utero nutrition (0 - parturition, negative control); (U2) 0 - 90 d of gestation; (U3) 90 - 180 d of gestation; (U4) 180 d - parturition; and (U5) in utero nutrition along gestation period (0 d to parturition - positive control) on the growth performance of the offspring to weaning age. The results indicated that effect of maternal nutrition on male and female offspring were particularly indicated by the growth performance of both the male and female offspring from birth to weaning.

Keywords : Bali cows, birth weight, maternal nutrition, pre-weaning daily gain, weaning weight

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